

**A CASE STUDY OF AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF GRIDHRASI
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SCIATICA**

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ABSTRACT

Gridhrasi, clinically correlatable to sciatica, is a major Vata vyadhi presenting with radiating pain, tingling, numbness, and functional disability.^[1] This case study documents the clinical presentation, Ayurvedic diagnosis, management and outcome of a 65-year-old female patient with left-sided Gridhrasi. An integrated approach involving Panchakarma, internal medications, and dietary interventions demonstrated marked improvement in symptoms and function. This case supports the efficacy of the Ayurvedic protocol in complex neuromuscular disorders where conventional therapies provide temporary or partial relief. The study underscores the holistic and multidisciplinary essence of Ayurveda in the management of chronic nerve compression disorders.

KEYWORDS: Gridhrasi, Sciatica, Ayurveda, Basti, Rasna Guggulu, Dashmool Kwath, Panchakarma, Vata vyadhi, Nerve pain.

INTRODUCTION

Gridhrasi is one of the eighty types of Vata vyadhi described in the Ayurvedic Samhitas. The classical definition includes pain radiating from the Sphik (buttock) through the Kati

(lumbar), Uru (thigh), Janu (knee), Jangha (calf) and Pada (foot), sometimes associated with tingling (“chimchimayan”), stiffness (“stambha”), limping movement (“vulture gait”), and functional limitations.^{[2],[3]}

” स्फिक्पूर्वा कटिपृष्ठोरुजानुजङ्घापदं क्रमात् ।

गृध्रसी स्तम्भरुक्तोदैर्गृह्णाति स्पन्दते मुहुः ॥

वाताद्वातकफात्तन्द्रागौरवारोचकान्विता ।”

च. चि. २८/५६, ५७

With rising age and sedentary lifestyle, the prevalence of sciatica is increasing globally. Modern science attributes sciatica to nerve root compression—commonly due to herniated lumbar disc, spondylosis, or degenerative lumbar spine disorders. Management in modern medicine includes NSAIDs, physiotherapy, steroids, and surgery, all with limited long-term efficacy and risk of side effects or recurrence. Ayurveda visualizes Gridhrasi as primarily a Vata vyadhi, often involving Kapha and sometimes Pittanubandha, with pathology rooted in vitiation of Vata dosha affecting the Majjavaha strotas (nervous system).^[4]

The present case analyses the Ayurvedic diagnosis, pathogenesis, and integrated management of a classical Gridhrasi patient and discusses the clinical outcomes within a holistic framework.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the effectiveness of Panchakarma procedures (Katibasti and Matrabasti), internal medications, and dietary regulation in improving symptoms and quality of life in Gridhrasi.

CASE STUDY

Patient Profile- A 65 yr Female patient approached to Kayachikitsa O.P.D. presenting with the following complaints,

- 1) Vama pada shula.
- 2) Vama pada chimchimayana.
- 3) Ubhaya janusanshi shula.

All symptoms occurred since 2 months.

History of Present Illness

The patient, a 65-year-old female, noticed a gradual onset of lower back pain extending down the left leg, aggravated with walking, standing, or prolonged sitting. Over time, the pain

worsened, associated with tingling, numbness, and intermittent exacerbations at night, impairing mobility. She had taken Allopathic and Homeopathic treatment for some complains but still she had no relief, so she admitted to kayachikitsa O.P.D. for treatment on 20/01/2025.

History of Past Illness

No history of trauma, fever, bowel or bladder disturbances.

No comorbid conditions (No DM, HTN, or thyroid disorder).

No any Past Medical, Surgical, and Family History

No significant family history or hereditary neuromuscular disorders.

No addictions or adverse dietary patterns.

No surgical interventions for the present complaint.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

General Physical Examination

BP: 130/80 mmHg

Pulse: 96/min

Weight: 66.5 kg

Height: 155 cm

BMI: 27.7 (Overweight)

Respi. rate: 18/min

Temp.: afebrile

Ashtavidha Pariksha

Nadi - 96/min

Mala - Samyak

Mutra - Samyak

Jivha - Ipasama (Kapha coated)

Netra - Shweta (normal)

Sparsha -samashitoshna

Druk - Spashta

Akruti - Madhyam (Average build)

INVESTIGATIONS:- (22/01/2025)

Test	Result	Reference range	Interpretation
Hemoglobin	9.9 g/dl	12–15 g/dl (F)	Mild anemia
Total Leukocyte	5190/cu.mm	4000–11000	Normal
Platelet	316000/cu.mm	1.5–4.0 lakhs	Normal
ESR	25mm/hr	<20 (F)	Mildly elevated
Random Blood Sugar	110.0 mg/dl	70–120 mg/dl	Normal
Blood Urea level	18mg/dl	10–40 mg/dl	Normal
Serum Creatinine	0.68 mg/dl	0.6–1.2 mg/dl	Normal
Serum Bilirubin	0.49 mg/dl	<1.2 mg/dl	Normal
SGOT	16.0 IU/L	5-40 U/L	Normal
SGPT	10.0 IU/L	7-56 U/L	Normal

Locomotor and Neurological Examination

Tenderness: Lumbo-sacral region and left lower limb

Restricted movement: Flexion/extension of the back, left hip, and knee

Straight Leg Raising (SLR): Positive on left side (<30°), indicative of sciatic nerve irritation

Muscle power: Slight reduction in left leg

Deep tendon reflexes: Preserved

Gait: Limping (“vulture-like”)

Systemic Examination

CVS: Normal

CNS: conscious and well oriented

Respiratory: Normal

Abdomen: Soft, non-tender

Samprapti Ghatakas

Dosha: Vata pradhana, with some Kapha association

Roga Marga: Madhyama

Dushya: Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Asthi, Majja

Adhishtana: Kati-pradesh (lumbar), Uru, Janu, Jangha, Pada

Srotas: Majja vaha srotas (neural channels)

Sadhya-Asadhyata: Krichha Sadhya (difficult but treatable chronic disorder)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Method:- 1) A case study

2) Centre:- P.G. Department of Kaychikitsa L.K. Ayurvedic Hospital, Yavatmal affiliated to

D.M.M. Ayurved College, Yavatmal.

MATERIAL

➤ **Sthanik Chikista:** *Katibasti* and *Janubasti* done on 22/01/2025.

Lepa : Dashang Lepa for (LA)

➤ **Shodhan Chikitsa:** **Matrabasti** (Saindhavadi Taila) (for 6 days).

➤ **Shaman Chikitsa**

Dravya	Dose	Duration	Anupan
Triphala Guggulu	500mg	Twice a day	Luke worm water
Rasna guggul	500mg	Twice a day	Luke worm water
Arogyavardhini vati	250mg	Twice a day	Luke worm water
Vatvidhwansa Rasa	250mg	Twice a day	Luke worm water
Ekangvir Rasa	250mg	Twice a day	Luke worm water
A Combination of Dashmool+ Rasna+ Punarnava+Ashwagandha	1gm each churna	Twice a day	Luke worm water
Panchasakar churna	3gm	HS	Luke worm water
Dashmool bharad kwath	30 ml	Twice a day	-
Dashang lepa	For local application	Twice a day	-

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND MONITORING

Outcome Parameter	Before Treatment	After 12 Days (Discharge)
VAS Pain Score	8/10	3/10
SLR (Straight Leg Raise)	<30°	>60°
Gait	Limping	Near normal
Tingling/Numbness	Severe	Mild / Intermittent
Muscle Weakness	Mild	Minimal
Daily Activities	Severely restricted	Improved
Anemia	Mild	Improved symptomatically
General Weakness	Present	Reduced

DISCUSSION

Yograj guggulu- These are mostly drugs that have effects like tikta, kashaya, katu rasa, ushna, ruksha guna, and ushna virya, and they also work as kaphavatahara. These medicines also work as vedana stapaka, nadi balya, shulashamaka, and shothahara, which is very important for helping people in vatavyadhi feel better. Because it has lekhana properties, Guggulu gets rid of too much jalansha.^[5]

Punarnava Guggulu- Punarnava Guggulu works anti-inflammatory and also which has pacifying Tridosha and indicated in especially acute swelling, also indicated in gout, rheumatoid arthritis, skin disorder.^[6]

Arogyavardhini Vati - Arogyavardhini works on the working of Pakwashaya and Grahani as a whole and makes it smooth and fine.^[7]

Dashmula Kwath– It is Tridosahara, Vedana sthapak and Sroto Shodhaka.

Rasna guggul - Vata-Kapha pacifying, analgesic, anti-inflammatory.^[8]

CONCLUSION

This case exemplifies the efficacy, safety, and holistic benefits of an integrated Ayurvedic approach in chronic Gridhrasi (sciatica). Panchakarma procedures like Kati basti, basti karma, and swedana, combined with targeted internal herbal-medico-mineral medications, delivered significant, sustained improvement in pain, mobility, and quality of life. This protocol minimized dependence on allopathic analgesics and did not result in any adverse medical events. A multidisciplinary team and patient-tailored dietary/lifestyle modification provided crucial support.

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